

Adapting to online education through project-based learning in a complex remote zone (Magallanes /Chile)

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Abstract

Faced with the health emergency caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus, the Chilean government declared a state of catastrophe due to public calamity throughout Chilean territory. The University of Magallanes, since the beginning of the 2020 academic year, has started online classes. Accelerated changes have been motivated the development of theoretical and practical classes in laboratories for both the Construction Engineering faculty and students. Forcing them to adapt to this new form and to face the learning of engineering from their homes. The purpose of this research was to evaluate the learning process carried out during the academic period, as well as the effectiveness of its implementation in a virtual model of the design of the General Construction and Structural Analysis I courses. One of the ways to learn about the student's perception of the implementation of the virtual learning was through a final survey on both subjects, that evaluated the criteria of internet quality, satisfaction with the activity carried out, and the quality of the item. In the General Construction course, the laboratory was evaluated by asking the students to build a scale model of a house. This was carried out through collaborative work in a project which was evaluated by items through photographs uploaded to the cloud. The passing rate of the students was 90.9%. For the Structural Analysis I course, we used the teaching methodology called "Design Thinking". The assignment consists of making models with accessible materials in their home and of which the structural models differ between an inverted catenary and a suspension bridge. The evaluation was through a video with teacher feedback. The students passing rate was 72.7%. The evaluation of the process through the survey was considered positive by the students.

Keywords: Online classes; Construction Engineering; Assessment; Project Based Learning.

1 Introduction

Given the health emergency caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus, the Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean (ECLAC) indicates that in the field of education, a large part of the measures adopted by the countries of the region in response to the crisis was the suspension of face-to-face classes at all levels. All these have originated the deployment of distance learning modalities, using a variety of formats and platforms (with or without the use of technology)(NU.CEPAL, 2020).

The University of Magallanes started the Virtual Development Unit (UDV) in 2014, which was created because of the need to have an educational option in the field of undergraduate, postgraduate, and continuing education for those located in geographically remote locations. Its purpose is to support the professional development of academic programmes in E-learning and B-learning modalities. Currently, the most widely used tools for the Construction Engineering program are the Moodle© platform (UMAG, 2020b) y Google Drive©.

In 2017, academic staff from the Faculty of Engineering (FI-UMAG) promoted the use of problem-based learning (PBL) in lessons to improve relevant aspects. These are linking with the environment and incorporating real problems which will lead to the comprehensive development and strengthening of soft skills (Lagos et al., 2018). A group of the academic staff was trained on PBL and they indicated that these activities have been used in their classes for some time and on a regular basis, but they were unaware of the concept. The use of PBL dates back to before the pandemic, as it poses a problem and develops problem-solving skills through self-directed learning. (González & del Valle López, 2008)(Barrows, 1986). This methodology is used in the General Construction (GC) course at UMAG. To assess the performance of the future engineer through the exchange of learning files and the use of collaborative work tools the evaluation was done through an E-Portfolio, a folder stored in Virtual Undergraduate or Google Drive© (Tapia Saucedo, 2013). As Paulson and

Paulson (Paulson & Paulson, 1991) said, "the portfolio is a laboratory where students construct the meaning of their accumulated experience". Therefore, academic staff used the e-portfolio as a tool to monitor and evaluate students' achievements (UC Berkeley, 2021) .

Another methodology used is Design Thinking (DT) which focuses on problem solving and applies to any field that requires a creative approach. This allows working in multidisciplinary teams to develop solutions openly and collaboratively way. It stimulates cooperation and creativity and breaks with established ideas to generate new innovative options to address problems or improve situations. Globally, it has become an indispensable method in the innovation process. It is used in companies such as Apple©, General Electric©, and Philips©, among others. Design Thinking is currently widely applied in business schools and innovation centres of universities such as Stanford, Berkeley, and MIT, among many others. (Levine et al., 2016) (Mabogunje et al., 2016).

In addition to spreading the DT methodology beyond engineering disciplines, and involving students in projects with a strong social impact, programmes are increasingly using the potential of the Internet and social media platforms to support open innovation processes on a larger scale (Steinbeck, 2011). This methodology was used in the Structural Analysis I (SA-I) course and the evaluation was through the use of a video. This video should provoke debate in the student when delivering the contents and analysis of what was requested by the academic staff (Jackson et al., 2013). Learners should be able to express knowledge, understanding, and reflection of the content (Campbell et al., 2019).

There are 3.6 million internet landlines in Chile with an annual growth of 5.5%, and 32.8% of these are through optic fiber technology, according to the latest statistics of the Sub-secretariat of Telecommunications (SUBTEL) for the first half of 2020 (SUBTEL, 2020). In the Magallanes region, the quality of internet in mobile and landline services shows deficiencies, such as a gradual decrease in internet speed and availability in certain sectors of Punta Arenas and nearby areas. In the survey of GC and SA-I students, it is highlighted that the main problems are highly variable internet speed and external factors, especially weather conditions. The development of virtual classrooms has made evident the lack of resources of the poor social sectors, (Llerena L. & Sánchez N., 2020). The strategies generated by UMAG were to provide internet accessibility and equipment to students who could not afford them and to be able to develop virtual classes

Under these conditions, both students and academic staff had to adjust to the changes and request technological support. In addition, we should mention that in the Magallanes region we were in an extensive territorial quarantine reaching 114 days. This caused a lack of motivation in the students to reach some soft skills for the development of their practical activities.

This research aims to analyze the teaching-learning adaptation of the lab workshop to the online format in the courses of General Construction (GC) and Structural Analysis I (SA-I). For the analysis, the following activities were carried out: literature review, application of an instrument to measure student's satisfaction with the virtual classes, and an evaluation. Here, we present the results and conclusions.

2 Methodology

2.1 Subjects characteristics

The Construction Engineering programme is based on the guidelines of the Educational Project for Institutions (PEDI) which focuses on competencies grouped into two categories, generic competencies and specific competencies (S). They establish the depth, scope, and precision of the expected learning. (UMAG, 2014).

Table 1 shows the specific competencies (S) of the 2 courses that will be analysed from the theoretical-practical integration. The "practical" part increases knowledge using laboratory and/or workshops, contextualizing the environment in which the future engineer will be involved (UMAG, 2020a). In the GC subject, students demonstrate general knowledge of constructive processes and codes governing the construction industry. The SA-I course teaches students to determine reactions and to draw internal stress diagrams. They should be able to understand the analysis of hyperstatic structures, apply design and calculation methods.

Table 1. Specific competencies (E) of the courses.

Subjects	CT*	Có d.	Competencies Involved
General Construction (GC)	3	S2 S4	Designing, conducting, and performing experiments as well as analyzing and interpreting their results. Working in multidisciplinary teams.
Structural Analysis I (SA-I)	3	S1 S5	Applying mathematic, scientific, and engineering knowledge Identifying, formulating, and solving engineering problems.

*transferable credits

2.2 Attendees

The students in the target population are in the 2nd and 3rd year of the Construction Engineering Program. Table 2 shows the number of students for each subject, the number of students by gender, by age range, and by passing rates.

Table 2. Number of students for each subject.

Subjects	Number			Age			% Passing Rate
	Total	Men(%)	Women(%)	19-20	21-22	23-24	
General Construction (CG)	11	81.2	18.2	67 %	11 %	22 %	90.9
Structural Analysis I (SA-I)	11	72.7	27.3	7%	50%	43 %	72.7

In addition, it was determined that most students live in the city of Punta Arenas with 93% of the total, while 7% live in Puerto Natales (see Figure 1.). Figure 2 shows the geographical location of the two cities, which are 248 km apart.

Figure 1. Area of the city of Punta Arenas where the students took their classes.

Figure 2. Location of the Magallanes region. (COMAPA, 2017)

2.3 Student attendance to online lessons

To know the participation of the students in the online lessons, we carried out a survey through a Google© form at the end of the academic year, whose objective was to know the type of internet connection they used and how they developed their online learning. The survey showed that 80% of the students had a landline internet plan at home and they used a laptop. When they lost the connection, 73% of the students answered that they went to someone else's home to solve the problem. In addition, if students were unable to participate in class, 27% "watched the recorded lesson asynchronously" and 53% "got the notes from their classmates for the lessons they had missed".

To determine the reliability of a measurement instrument, we determined the Cronbach's alpha coefficient by using an Excel© spreadsheet for data analysis. The questionnaire contained five questions and five response options, using the Likert scale (1. Never, 2. Occasionally, 3. Sometimes, 4. Frequently, 5. Always) and 13 questions with Likert scale (1. Very Dissatisfied, 2. Dissatisfied, 3. Neither Satisfied/Nor Dissatisfied, 4. Satisfied,

5. Very Satisfied). The alpha coefficient values obtained for the GC course was 0.93 and for the SA-I course it was 0.89 which indicates an excellent internal consistency (Cronbach, 1951) (Frias-Navarro, 2020).

Figure 3. shows the assessment of the main factors that affected the students when they started the online lessons. The survey showed that the main problems were the variable internet speed and some external factors, especially the weather conditions.

Figure 3. Estimation of the main factors that affected the students.

The second part of the survey determined whether the students recognize any difference in their learning in the online lessons. In this second section, we evaluated whether the laboratory work of the subject was a) useful, b) entertaining, c) could be done in groups, d) helped to consolidate knowledge, and e) was a good complement to the theory. We also asked if the workload for the course was adequate, the help and follow-up were sufficient, and whether the instructions were clear.

Figure 4. shows that 80% of the students rated the course laboratories positively, being a complement to the theory and an entertaining activity. Regarding the tasks to be carried out, 60% of the students answered that the instructions were clear and 55% of them agreed that the workload was adequate. The alternative with the lowest evaluation corresponds to teamwork, which only reached 40%.

Figure 4. Degree of satisfaction of the practical virtual classes GC and SA-I.

2.4 Satisfaction with the laboratories

For the GC subject, the survey had a third section, which was a rubric asking about satisfaction using a framework that sets out criteria and standards for different levels of performance and describes what performance would look like at each level. The rubric is an element created before starting online lessons because of the pandemic and was used in the same way during this period. This showed that the students in general terms are very satisfied, as can be seen in

Figure 5. The rubric served as a guide for them to prepare their work, providing the main elements to develop. Students expressed 85% satisfaction in this aspect. In addition, the assessment guideline was easy to understand and helped them to improve their work, both aspects reached 72% of satisfaction.

Figure 5. Degree of satisfaction with the rubric of the GC laboratory classes.

2.5 Activity design

Each subject was supported in the virtual classroom of the UMAG Campus – Pregrado Virtual (Moodle©), Google Drive©, and Classroom© where instructions, news, contents, guides, and evaluation were coordinated in a general way. In short, a technological variety of tools have been created for the development of collaborative work. The virtual classes were held via Meet©.

The laboratory of the GC subject is based on the application of a PBL type activity and the online evaluation was carried out through the use of an E-Portfolio. The problem was: *"the housing deficit in the region of Magallanes and Chilean Antarctica, according to the CASEN survey 2017 was 3.601units. (CChC, 2018); to improve this index and increase the employment rate under the pandemic conditions. The state has invested \$36 MM for the construction of 1,225 social housing units in 11 lots in the last year (MINVU, 2020). Despite this, the deficit continues. Based on this problem, a construction engineer, owner of a construction company, must design a housing solution for those citizens who cannot access state housing subsidies. For this, they must take into account the following: i) Surface area of the dwelling, ii) Construction systems and types of materials and iii) Project execution time". The use of an E-Portfolio is an appropriate tool to consolidate collaborative learning and facilitates academic work. This activity was called "Construction of a single-family house". The purpose was to keep learning resources, feedback, and the students' entry records updated during the semester.*

In the subject SA-I, the laboratory is based on the application of an activity using Design Thinking. This activity is the following: *"For the application of this teaching model, the student must answer the following question: What is the difference between an inverted catenary and a suspension bridge? To answer this question, each student must study both structural models, propose the design of two structures, one using the inverted catenary as a model and the other one must correspond to a suspension structure. Both designs must support a load of 1 kg. The models can be made with materials of your choice". The online assessment was carried out employing a video, in which the student had to edit and explain the difference between the two structural systems and what each of the designed models consists of. Also, they had to explain how it was executed and demonstrate that the models can withstand the requested load. With the results obtained, the students had to draw their own conclusions, which were later discussed with the whole class, guided by the teacher.*

3 Experiences and Results

The GC subject was historically conducted in the laboratory and the main competencies are presented in Table 1. The students should understand the fundamental elements of design in order to interpret the results, through teamwork. Figure 6 shows the working diagram of the Problem-Based Learning (PBL), where the didactic strategy used is important and the role of the students consisted of their participation in the process of evaluation and design of their knowledge. In summary: Step 1 - House design: the student presents the project of a single-family house; architectural plan, foundations, and wooden structure; Step 2 - Construction company: the learner organises and plans the functions of the company that will carry out the construction work of the "sketch"; Step 3 - Inspection: the student assistant monitors the work through weekly progress of

the "model" and review of the work book (through the use of the portfolio) and Step 4 - Construction of the house model: at the end of the semester the student will deliver the model, by means of a photographic set and defense by Meet©.

We concluded that in the laboratories, the students studied the construction systems every week and presented the progress of their models. They also exchanged the experiences of the work they had done and solved their problems among themselves. The contribution of all this is that it develops and shapes a self-taught culture in the students with respect to their learning, applying the capacity for organization, creativity, and responsibility. In addition, it strengthens the links between the online lessons and the participative work between the students, the assistant, and the teacher. All this led to the development of oral expression, the strengthening of character, and meeting the project's scheduled times.

Figure 6. Wooden house construction work-flow.

To produce the models for the SA-I subject, the students followed the following steps: i) Research of the topic, ii) Analysis and calculation of the results, iii) Choice of the materials to be used in the model, and iv) Production of the model.

Figure 7. Theory of the catenary v/s parable.

According to the phases of DT, in the first one the student explains the concept of catenary and parabola, and in which type of structures they are used, i.e., empathises and defines the concepts to be used in order to create the project that solves the problem being viable and meaningful. (Villarroel et al., 2017) (see Figure 7).

Analysis and materials.

Figure 8. a) Calculation of a suspension bridge, by means of the parable and b) Materials for the elaboration of the model.

When carrying out the analysis and later the calculation (see Figure 8. a) the students executed their design firstly in sketches that served as a guide for the construction and/or elaboration of the model. In the Figure 8 b) the students could choose the materials for the model, prioritizing the use of disused-recycled materials found at home. In this phase, students developed the model and tested the prototypes with 1 kg (Villarrol et al., 2017).

Models

Figure 9.a) Arch created by using the catenary and b) Suspension bridge, using the parable.

Each student built 2 models representing the concept catenary structure and suspension bridge, respectively. In phase 3 of the DT method, the solution is evaluated, in this case, it is 100% technical by fulfilling the resistance with 1 kg (eg: sugar, flour, etc.) Figure 9.a)

At the end of the activity, all students presented their work to the class, generating a discussion of the observations and results obtained individually. All of this was guided by the teacher responsible for the subject.

In summary, this research helped us determine the existence of gaps such as access to connectivity, digital skills (teacher-students), and skills in teaching methodologies. Added to this is the resilience of students and teachers who now need more time to comply with scheduled activities. Based on this, future classes will be a mixture of face-to-face laboratories and online theoretical classes. We will have to work and adapt to learning experiences through technology.

4 Conclusion

This research is summarized in two parts, the adaptation of the laboratory to online lessons throughout the 2020 academic year and the perception of the students using a survey.

Regarding the laboratories, the students considered that they are a complement to the theory and an entertaining activity. Despite having a variable speed internet connection, some of the students indicated that they "watched the videos later" and some that they "shared their notes with their classmates".

The perception of the faculty is also important as they had to redesign the practical experiences and adapt them to the online format. In addition, the autonomy in their learning process often did not happen due to the

lack of motivation of the students at the beginning of the pandemic and the switch to distance learning. But despite that, the students managed to develop their organizational skills, creativity, and responsibility in fulfilling the objectives set in the different activities. They also had to deal with another problem which was the access to the materials to make the models, since the local shops were closed due to their lock down (over 114 days), which meant that they had to use recycled materials found at home.

Concerning the teaching methodologies used in the GC/PBL and SA-I/DT subjects, both were implemented even though they were based on collaborative work and that the students worked most of the time from their homes and met in the virtual classroom once a week. They managed to understand and relate the concepts. And they developed greater autonomy in their learning process.

Finally, this research focused on the transformation of the teaching-learning processes from face-to face to the online format. Despite the problems detected by both students and faculty, considering the emergency caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, the results of the process experienced are positive.

5 References

- Barrows, H. S. (1986). A taxonomy of problem-based learning methods. *Medical education*, 20(6), 481-486.
- Campbell, L. O., Heller, S., & DeMara, R. F. (2019). Implementing Student-Created Video in Engineering: An Active Learning Approach for Exam Preparedness. *UEP*, 9(4), 63-75.
- CChC. (2018). Déficit habitacional: Un desafío pendiente. *Cámara Chilena de la Construcción*, 18.
- COMAPA. (2017). *Comapa Turismo* [https://comapa.com/parque-del-estrecho-de-magallanes]. https://comapa.com/parque-del-estrecho-de-magallanes
- González, A. E., & del Valle López, Á. (2008). *El aprendizaje basado en problemas: Una propuesta metodológica en educación superior* (Vol. 18). Narcea Ediciones.
- Jackson, N., Quinn, D., Lonie, A., Rathore, P., & James, P. (2013). Video in engineering courses to promote active online learning environments. *Proceedings of A2E2 conference Gold Coast*. Retrieved from https://www.engineersaustralia.org.au/australasian-association-engineering-education/2013-annualconference.
- Lagos, R., Calisto, N., Navarro, D., Maldonado, P., Alberti, P., Villarroel, J., Vivar, B., & Loyola, F. (2018). EFEI, an interdisciplinary cowork in the Engineering Faculty—University of Magallanes—Chile. *International Symposium on Project Approaches in Engineering Education*, 8.
- Levine, D. I., Agogino, A. M., & Lesniewski, M. A. (2016). Design thinking in development engineering. *International Journal of Engineering Education*, 32(3), 1396-1406.
- Llerena L., R., & Sánchez N., C. (2020). Educación rural en el Perú, entre la desigualdad y la pandemia: Desafíos para la educación virtual. *Presencia, miradas desde y hacia la educación*, 5.
- Mabogunje, A., Sonalkar, N., & Leifer, L. (2016). Design thinking: A new foundational science for engineering. *International Journal of Engineering Education*, 32(3), 1540-1556.
- MINVU. (2020, diciembre 22). *MINVU anuncia inversión por 36 mil millones de pesos en viviendas sociales para Magallanes en 2021*. [Www.ovejeronoticias.cl]. https://www.ovejeronoticias.cl/2020/12/minvu-anuncia-inversion-por-36-mil-millones-de-pesos-en-viviendas-sociales-para-magallanes-en-2021/
- NU.CEPAL. (2020). *La educación en tiempos de la pandemia de COVID-19* (p. 21). CEPAL UNESCO.
- Paulson, P. R., & Paulson, F. L. (1991). *Portfolios: Stories of Knowing*.
- Steinbeck, R. (2011). El «design thinking» como estrategia de creatividad en la distancia. *Comunicar*, 19(37), 27-35.
- SUBTEL. (2020, octubre 5). Conexiones de internet fija crecen 5,5% en Chile en junio 2020. *Subsecretaría de Telecomunicaciones*. https://www.subtel.gob.cl/conexiones-de-internet-fija-crecen-55-en-chile-a-junio-de-2020/
- Tapia Saucedo, P. (2013). *Uso del portafolio electrónico como herramienta para facilitar la labor académica de la Facultad de Ingeniería de Sistemas e Informática de la Universidad Nacional de San Martín-Tarapoto*.
- UC Berkeley. (2021). E-Portfolio. *Center for Teaching & Learning*. https://teaching.berkeley.edu/resources/assessment-and-evaluation/design-assessment/e-portfolio
- UMAG. (2014). DECRETO N°10/SU/2014—Oficializa Nuevo Texto del Proyecto Educativo Institucional. *Universidad de Magallanes*, 25.
- UMAG. (2020a). Decreto N°012/SU/2020—Actualiza rediseño carrera Ingeniería en Construcción con salida intermedia de Técnico en Edificación, en la Universidad de Magallanes, como se indica. *Universidad de Magallanes*, 26.
- UMAG. (2020b). *Pregrado Virtual*. Universidad de Magallanes. https://pregradovirtual.umag.cl
- Villarroel, R., Spencer, H., & Muñoz, R. (2017). Aplicación de design thinking de manera interdisciplinaria en la asignatura de ingeniería de software. *Memorias XXX Congreso SOCHEDI*, 1-9.